

Waste to Wealth..! Biogas Production from Food Waste

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Accepted August 10,2021

Published August 16,2021

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5204441>

Pages: 47-49

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How to cite this article (APA):

Narththanah, S., & Sajuran, K. (2021). Waste to Wealth..! Biogas Production from Food Waste. *North American Academic Research*, 4(8), 47-49. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5204441>

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

The Up-flow Anaerobic Sludge Blanket Reactor (UASBR) is widely used due to its high potential in converting the food waste to bio-gas. Long start-up periods and inhibitions due to high ion concentrations are common issues of UASBRs. Therefore, a prototype UASBR was designed and developed by incorporating biofilter liner system to address these issues. This study was conducted for 40 days to evaluate the performance of UASBR with the modifications in the feeding system, recirculation system, and newly established sludge removal port. Food waste was prepared with the proper elemental composition based on the calculations done by solving the Linear Programming Problem (LPP). Reactor performance was evaluated daily by analysing the physical and biochemical parameters. Interventions such as addition of 1M KOH, inoculum and food waste, recirculation, and sludge removal were done to enhance the anaerobic digestion and to accelerate the start-up process. All the parameters fluctuated responding to the interventions. Even though, pH was low inside the reactor, the methane gas production showed steady increase because methanogenic bacteria have started to adapt and acclimatize in the low pH environment. The colour of permeate was also a colourless solution. Also, towards the end of test period, total nitrogen, nitrate-nitrogen, available phosphorous, and total potassium were detected in permeate. Thus, the composite liner system acts as a live biofilter providing optimum conditions in the anaerobic digestion process via reducing the inhibitions and accelerating the start-up process.

Keywords: FOOD WASTE, BIO GAS, BIO-FILTER LINER SYSTEM, UP-FLOW ANAEROBIC SLUDGE BLANKET REACTOR

Introduction

An increase in food waste amount is related to a rise in population and living standard improvements of people over the years which has resulted in severe issues in both developing and developed countries. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, 2019, 1.3 billion tonnes of food production are wasted every year and it is one-third of world food production.

Daily, a large quantity of food waste is generated at different stages along with the food supply chain due to several reasons such as inadequate harvesting techniques, improper post-harvesting techniques, unsafe

packaging, and lack of knowledge on food processing, and not following the suitable food conservation methods and weaknesses in the prevailing institutional and legal frameworks.

Food supply chain

Is it possible to produce biogas from food waste?

Yes!

Biogas production is a sustainable way of food waste management because food waste contains a large amount of easily biodegradable organic matter, has a high amount of nutrient components and energy.

Materials and methods

Towards an efficient and effective way of biogas production

The Up-flow Anaerobic Sludge Blanket Reactor (UASBR) is widely used because of its high potential to convert food waste into biogas. High ionic concentrations and long start-up periods are its common issues. To solve this, a prototype reactor with a bio-filter liner system was established in 2018. It was rehabilitated by establishing a sludge removal port, modifying the feeding system and recirculation system. Performance evaluation was conducted for 40 days with different interventions to accelerate the start-up process.

Established UASBR

Conclusion

Impact of research results & the way forward!!!

Modifications to the reactor did considerable influence to accelerate the start-up process. Also, the pH particularly was an influential parameter which was intervened to increase the low pH values. Even though pH was low inside the reactor, the methane gas production showed steady increase. The composite liner acts as a live biofilter to make anaerobic system biologically stable. It is necessary to evaluate the performance of the UASBR with more interventions for a long period, in order to develop a pilot-scale UASBR and to commercialize it.

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